

FINITE ELEMENT MODELLING APPROACH FOR THE CURE OF AN EPOXY RESIN BY TAKING INTO ACCOUNT COUPLING EFFECTS BETWEEN CHEMISTRY, DIFFUSION, THERMAL AND MECHANICS

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SUMMARY: A macroscopic continuum formulation is proposed in order to describe the behaviour of a class of structural epoxy resin during its cure. This work is developed in the framework of thermodynamics of irreversible processes with generalized normality rule and small perturbations assumption. The elementary volume is composed of as a classical mixture of epoxy resin. The constitutive equations are explained for a mechanical behavior taking into account the viscoelasticity of the matter. Our purpose is to introduce a simple way for the taking into account of the connections between chemical, thermal, and mechanical phenomena acting during the chemical reaction of thermosetting.

KEYWORDS: standard model, coupled equations, thermosetting reaction, epoxy cure.

INTRODUCTION

The use of composites today at structural ends becomes increasingly important in the industry. These trend appears recently in naval construction, since the optimization of the structures became inevitable and requires a very precise knowledge of the material characteristics and also its internal state obtained at the end of the manufacturing process. For example, during the cure of a composite, internal stresses are generated and several imperfections (bubbles, fibres waviness...) may appear, decreasing therefore mechanical performances of the final material. These phenomena are taken a consequent aspect in the manufacturing of thick composites with long fibres. Indeed, at the end of the operation of cure the presence of fibres regularly corrugated within the plies can be observed. In thin composites it seems that this phenomenon is also active as suggested by the works of Paluch [1] for the case of long carbon fibres. This author clearly showed that, at the end of the cure, fibres are presented in an undulatory form. Jochum [2] proposed an explanation of this phenomenon: during the thermosetting reaction of the resin, the volume shrinkage associated to the phase change from the initial liquid state to the solid state induces a compressive loading onto the fibre which is destabilized and is therefore subjected to a buckle instability (microbuckling phenomenon). Internal stresses generating these undulation defects during the cure of a composite matrix result from a complex process where *thermal, physicochemical,*

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viscosity and *mechanical* phenomena are mixed. Additionally, this complexity is increased by the both thermo activated and exothermal behaviours of the thermosetting chemical reaction of the resin. Moreover throughout the cure, mechanical characteristics are evolving with temperature and degree of conversion of the chemical reaction.

Therefore, the construction of simulation tools for the process of cure requires the development of coupling models in order to take into account the mechanics, the thermal, the diffusion and the chemistry. From a theoretical point of view, these four aspects of the problem were generally approached separately. Models of coupling between the thermal and the chemical kinetics exist [3] and [4]. Some works of modelling for the process of pultrusion can be observed and the authors approached these couplings in a consequent way [5]. Tools using advanced finite elements made their appearance [6]. However these tools are established on formulations where all the couplings are not taken into account. Moreover the chemical reaction is generally approached as a scalar relation covering the degree of conversion only. But works on chemical reactions [7] showed that according to the initial mixture of the component parts, the chemical reaction kinetics vary, and initial heterogeneities of the fractions of the components induce diffusion of the different elements. These phenomena strongly influence the characteristics of the matter all over the cure, as well as at the end of it. The modelling of these phenomena coupled with the temperature and with the mechanics seems to be never having been approached before. The general thrust of this work is to give a formulation *as simple as possible* of some basic couplings.

It will lead us to discuss the possibility of linking thermal, diffusion and mechanical phenomena together and to evaluate rapidly the effects of such coupling. The set of local balance equations and resulting constitutive laws in viscoelastic framework is detailed hereafter. The framework of generalized standard mediums was chosen in order to simplify future numerical developments devoted to industrial software.

MODELLING APPROACH PRESENTATION

System description

The system is supposed being a traditional continuous medium, made up with a mixture of resin, hardener and accelerator [8]. The macroscopic representative elementary volume (REV) is considered homogeneous, open and characterized by averaged physical units defining the mixture. Thus, only the averaged behavior of the REV is involved here. It is an acceptable assumption, since experiments of mechanical characterization exhibit only the macroscopic behavior. The diffusion of each “species” is assumed to be described by a molecular diffusion phenomenon following a Fick law type. It is controlled by the gradients of concentration or mass ratio of the various species. In this REV the various elements react between them in order to create the matrix. This evolution of the mixture, governed by the equations of the diffusion and the equations of the chemistry, is taken into account in the equations of the thermal and of the mechanics.

Mass balance

By noting ρ the density of mixture, Y_i the mass fraction of each species (where the subscript $i = p$ denotes the resin; $i = a$ denotes the accelerator, $i = d$ denotes the hardener, $i = m$ denotes the obtained matrix), M_i the current molar mass of the species i and \mathbf{J}_i^m the associated relative mass flow, ν_{ir} the stoichiometric coefficient of the component part i for the reaction r , w_r the reaction rate for the reaction r , the mass balance of the component part i which leads to the equation of distribution of the corresponding species is as Eqn. 1:

$$\rho \dot{Y}_i = \sum_r \nu_{ir} M_i w_r - \text{div}(\mathbf{J}_i^m) \quad (1)$$

where ‘ $\dot{\cdot}$ ’ denotes the time derivative function and div the divergence operator. In order to simplify the modeling approach a unique reaction is only taken into consideration ($r = 1$), in spite of the fact that many reactions are evolving during the thermosetting reaction of an epoxy resin. Moreover the accelerator mass ratio, which is very low in comparison with other current species, can be neglected for Eqn. 1. On the other hand, its effect is reintroduced through the kinetics law of the chemical reaction rate. These assumptions do not reduce the generality of model.

The total mass conservation in the REV leads to a relation between the mass ratio of the resin, of the hardener and of the obtained matrix, which is written as following:

$$Y_m + Y_p + Y_d = 1 \quad (2)$$

This relation is used in the formalism to simplify the expressions.

Mechanical balance

In regular points of the non-polar body, the mechanical balance leads to the classical equation of movement Eqn. 3 where $\boldsymbol{\sigma}$ denotes the Cauchy stress tensor applied onto the mixture and \mathbf{f} denotes the mass density of forces applied onto the REV. Accelerations have been neglected because the cure is supposed being a quite a slow process.

$$\text{div } \boldsymbol{\sigma} + \rho \mathbf{f} = 0 \quad (3)$$

Thermodynamic balance, state laws

The total energy conservation of the system, as described by the first principle of thermodynamics, is expressed locally in the following traditional form:

$$\rho \dot{u} = \boldsymbol{\sigma} : \dot{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}} - \text{div } \mathbf{J}_q + r \quad (4)$$

where ‘ u ’ is the specific internal energy of the mixture, $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}$ the infinitesimal strain tensor associated with the mixture, \mathbf{J}_q the heat flux and r the external heat supply per unit volume. Note that ‘ $:$ ’ denotes the double contract product.

The thermodynamic system is assumed been close to its equilibrium. The classical assumption of a local accompanying state allows us to describe at any time the state of a given material EV by a set of state variables. One admits first the existence of one homogeneous absolute temperature T valid for the mixture and for all its constituents. In classical linear viscoelasticity framework, total strain is classically separated into elastic and inelastic (non reversible) components, denoted $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^e$ and $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^v$ respectively, like $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon} = \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^e + \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^v$.

From a constitutive law point of view, a Kelvin-Voigt model was considered and this mechanical model assumes also a partition of the stress tensor $\boldsymbol{\sigma}$ as $\boldsymbol{\sigma} = \boldsymbol{\sigma}^{an} + \boldsymbol{\sigma}^{vr}$, containing an inelastic part $\boldsymbol{\sigma}^{an}$ and a viscous reversible part $\boldsymbol{\sigma}^{vr}$. Of course, it is a first level model to represent a viscoelastic behavior for a polymer, but the aim of this paper is to present a modelling approach. It is clear that it cannot be used to predict exactly the complete mechanical behaviour evolution of the mixture during the cure. However, it could be effective by taking into account the effect of temperature and degree of cure on mechanical characteristics, while restricting the implementation work in a finite element industrial code (F.E.M. analysis).

Thus, assumptions presented before allow the material state to be defined by following variables: temperature T , elastic and viscous strains, $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^e$ and $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^v$, resin and hardener mass ratios Y_p and Y_d . The specific free energy potential ψ depending on all these variables $\psi = \psi(T, \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^e, \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^v, Y_p, Y_d)$ and under the assumption of a normal parameter setting [9], laws can be established. By considering the framework of small perturbations, i.e. infinitesimal strains and

few thermal and mass variations, the second order development of the potential ψ allows the construction of *coupling linear behaviour* laws as following :

$$\begin{aligned}
\boldsymbol{\sigma} &= \boldsymbol{\sigma}_0 + \lambda^0 (\text{tr } \boldsymbol{\epsilon}^e) \mathbf{I} + 2\mu^0 \boldsymbol{\epsilon}^e - 3K^0 [\alpha_T^0 \Delta T - \alpha_{dm}^0 \Delta Y_d - \alpha_{pm}^0 \Delta Y_p] \mathbf{I} \\
s &= s_0 + \frac{C}{T_0} \Delta T + \frac{3K^0 \alpha_T^0}{\rho} (\text{tr } \boldsymbol{\epsilon}^e) + \frac{3K^\infty \alpha_T^\infty}{\rho} (\text{tr } \boldsymbol{\epsilon}^v) + D_{Tm} \Delta Y_d + D_{Tp} \Delta Y_p \\
\mu_m &= \mu_m^0 - D_{md} \Delta Y_d - D_{mp} \Delta Y_p - \frac{3K^0 \alpha_m^0}{\rho} \text{tr } \boldsymbol{\epsilon}^e - \frac{3K^\infty \alpha_m^\infty}{\rho} \text{tr } \boldsymbol{\epsilon}^v - \frac{D_{mT}}{\rho} \Delta T + RT \log(\gamma_m Y_m)^{\Gamma_m} \\
\mu_d &= \mu_d^0 + D_{dm} \Delta Y_d + D_{dmp} \Delta Y_p - \frac{3K^0 \alpha_d^0}{\rho} \text{tr } \boldsymbol{\epsilon}^e - \frac{3K^\infty \alpha_d^\infty}{\rho} \text{tr } \boldsymbol{\epsilon}^v - \frac{D_{dT}}{\rho} \Delta T + RT \log(\gamma_d Y_d)^{\Gamma_d} \quad (5) \\
\mu_p &= \mu_p^0 + D_{pmd} \Delta Y_d + D_{pmp} \Delta Y_p - \frac{3K^0 \alpha_p^0}{\rho} \text{tr } \boldsymbol{\epsilon}^e - \frac{3K^\infty \alpha_p^\infty}{\rho} \text{tr } \boldsymbol{\epsilon}^v - \frac{D_{pT}}{\rho} \Delta T + RT \log(\gamma_p Y_p)^{\Gamma_p} \\
\boldsymbol{\sigma}^{vr} &= \boldsymbol{\sigma}_0^{vr} + \lambda^\infty (\text{tr } \boldsymbol{\epsilon}^v) \mathbf{I} + 2\mu^\infty \boldsymbol{\epsilon}^v - 3K^\infty [\alpha_T^\infty \Delta T - \alpha_{dm}^\infty \Delta Y_d - \alpha_{pm}^\infty \Delta Y_p] \mathbf{I} \\
3K^0 &= 3\lambda^0 + 2\mu^0 ; 3K^\infty = 3\lambda^\infty + 2\mu^\infty ; \Delta T = T - T_0 ; \Delta Y_d = Y_d - Y_d^0 ; \Delta Y_p = Y_p - Y_p^0 ; \alpha_{ij}^\infty = \\
&\quad \alpha_i^\infty - \alpha_j^\infty ; \alpha_{ij}^0 = \alpha_i^0 - \alpha_j^0
\end{aligned}$$

where T_0 , Y_i^0 , $\boldsymbol{\sigma}_0$, s_0 and μ_i^0 denote respectively initial values for temperature, mass ratio of species i , stress tensor, specific entropy and chemical potential of each species. The parameters λ^0 , μ^0 , λ^∞ , μ^∞ denote respectively instantaneous and long term Lamé's coefficients. The scalar C is the specific heat at constant strain and mass ratios, D_{ij} , D_{ijk} , α_i^0 , α_i^∞ are coefficients denoting coupling effects between thermodynamical forces and state variables associated with different phenomenon (diffusion, thermal, mechanic). The operator trace of a tensor is noted 'tr'. Coefficients γ_i and Γ_i are introduced in order to obtain a non linear chemical kinetic similar to [11]. In these laws, chemical potentials depend on the hydrostatic pressure (products of bulk modulus with volume strains), which is the consequence of the mechanical loading combined with the boundary conditions applied to the structure. Moreover the Kelvin-Voigt model allows us to consider both instantaneous and long time coupling effects. Although the framework is linear, the possibilities of the models are interesting. In a more traditional way, the stress tensors are directly influenced by the change of volume mass fraction, which depend on diffusion and degree of cure. Consequently this coupling interacts directly in the equations of diffusion as detailed on next paragraph. In order to improve more the model, intrinsic dependences must be integrated into the different characteristic parameters. However the protocol of parameter identification of the matrix thermo-mechanical behaviour during its formation should take into account these various couplings.

Entropy description – second principle

Opened systems whose evolution is in progress are considered here. The mass entropy s , associated to any representative element of mass of the mixture, is defined as a homogeneous first degree function of the extensive parameters which are the internal specific energy u of the mixture, the elastic strain tensor $\boldsymbol{\epsilon}^e$ and the mass ratio of the Y_i components. Within the general framework of opened systems, the total differential of the mass entropy checks the fundamental Gibbs generalized Eqn. 6, where local variation of entropy is expressed as follows:

$$T \dot{s} = \dot{u} - \frac{1}{\rho} \boldsymbol{\sigma} : \dot{\boldsymbol{\epsilon}}^e - \mu_m \dot{Y}_m - \mu_p \dot{Y}_p - \mu_d \dot{Y}_d \quad (6)$$

Taking into account first principle of the thermodynamics, fundamental relation of Gibbs and equations of diffusion, local variation of entropy (\dot{s}_e , Eqn.7) due to the outside exchanges and entropy variation related to internal evolutions (\dot{s}_i) is obtained. Volume dissipation Φ

established from the internal entropy production can be decomposed into four contributions and must check therefore the fundamental inequality of the second principle (Eqn. 7):

$$\rho \dot{s}_e = -\operatorname{div} \mathbf{J}_s + \frac{r}{T} \quad \mathbf{J}^s = \frac{1}{T} \mathbf{J}^q - \sum_{i=m,d,p} \frac{\mu_i}{T} \cdot \mathbf{J}_i^m M_i w_r \quad (7)$$

$$\varphi = \rho T \dot{s}_i = \boldsymbol{\sigma} : \dot{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}^v - \mathbf{J}^s \cdot \nabla T - \sum_{i=m,d,p} \mathbf{J}_i^m \cdot \nabla \mu_i + \sum_{i=m,d,p} \mu_i v_{ir} M_i w_r \geq 0$$

The first part of φ corresponds to the dissipation generated by the viscous phenomena of the mixture, and the two following parts are the quantities respectively associated to the gradient of temperature (heat transfer) and to the gradient of chemical potential (mass transport). The last part corresponds to the chemical reaction.

Potential of dissipation - Complementary constitutive equations

A second potential is introduced in order to define the evolution laws, namely the *pseudo-potential of dissipation*, more exactly its dual form \mathbf{d}^* that can be written as a function of $(\boldsymbol{\sigma}^{an}, -\nabla T, -\nabla \mu_i, \alpha_r)$ obtained by a Legendre-Fenchel transformation. If dissipation phenomena are supposed being governed by linear laws (small perturbations close to the thermodynamic equilibrium) and by the assumption of the validity of the Curie principle, the dual potential \mathbf{d}^* can be expressed under a quadratic form and evolution laws are:

$$\dot{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}^v = \frac{1 + \nu^v}{E^v} \boldsymbol{\sigma}^{an} - \frac{\nu^v}{E^v} \operatorname{tr}(\boldsymbol{\sigma}^{an}) \mathbf{I} + \mathbf{c}_{rs} \alpha_r \mathbf{I}$$

$$\mathbf{J}_d^m = -\mathbf{k}_d^\mu \nabla(\mu_d - \mu_m) - \mathbf{c}_{pm}^{\mu\mu} \cdot \nabla(\mu_p - \mu_m) - \mathbf{c}_d^{\mu T} \nabla T \quad \mathbf{J}^s = -\mathbf{k}_T \nabla T - \mathbf{c}_{dm}^{T\mu} \nabla(\mu_d - \mu_m) - \mathbf{c}_{pm}^{T\mu} \nabla(\mu_p - \mu_m) \quad (8)$$

$$\mathbf{J}_p^m = -\mathbf{k}_p^\mu \nabla(\mu_p - \mu_m) - \mathbf{c}_{dm}^{\mu\mu} \cdot \nabla(\mu_d - \mu_m) - \mathbf{c}_p^{\mu T} \nabla T \quad w_r = R_{dir} [1 - K^{-1} \prod_{i=m,d,p} (\gamma_i Y_i)^{M_{0i} \Gamma_i}] + \mathbf{c}_{rs} \operatorname{tr} \boldsymbol{\sigma}^{an}$$

Where tensors \mathbf{k}_T , \mathbf{k}_d^μ and \mathbf{k}_p^μ are the ‘Fourier’ and ‘Fick’ tensors. Tensors \mathbf{c}_{uv}^{ij} and coupling scalar c_{rs} , are not classical. Rambert et al. [10] have shown that the effect of coupling between thermal and diffusion on the response of a polymer structure can be neglected. The law expressing to the rate of degree of conversion of the reaction is similar to [11]. R_{dir} is the cure rate and K is the equilibrium constant of the chemical reaction. The coefficients can be modulated by the temperature as proposed by [11]. By choosing another potential of dissipation and another expression of the free energy, the traditional equations of the literature can be obtained. The innovation here comes from the taking into account of the direct couplings, which are interacting on the rate of degree of conversion of the reaction since it is influenced by the inelastic hydrostatic pressure. The thermosetting reaction depends on the chemical potentials of the various species, which are connected by the state laws to the mass fraction of the species, the temperature and the state of the volume strain within the matter. These couplings induce non-traditional effects of acceleration or deceleration on the chemical reaction. The viscous flow is also modulated by the reaction and this induces an indirect effect on the material behaviour. These effects are perhaps second order effects, but they have to be considered in order to identify the viscous behaviour throughout the cure.

Discussion about the couplings in the equation of heat and the equation of diffusion

By noting \mathbf{J}^q the heat flow and r the external sources of heat (radiation), the equation of heat containing all the couplings in the field of linear viscoelasticity can then be written under following expression:

$$\rho C \dot{T} = -\operatorname{div} \mathbf{J}^q + r + \boldsymbol{\sigma}^{an} : \dot{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}^v - T \{3K^0 \alpha_T^0 \mathbf{I} : \dot{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}^e + 3K^\infty \alpha_T^\infty \mathbf{I} : \dot{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}^v\} \quad (9)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& + \rho \left\{ T \left(\frac{D_{mT}}{\rho} - \frac{D_{dT}}{\rho} - R \log(\gamma_m Y_m)^{\Gamma_m} + R \log(\gamma_d Y_d)^{\Gamma_d} \right) - (\mu_d^0 - \mu_m^0 + (D_{dm} + D_{md}) \Delta Y_d + (D_{dmp} \right. \\
& \quad \left. + D_{mp}) \Delta Y_p - \frac{3K^0 (\alpha_d^0 - \alpha_m^0)}{\rho} \text{tr} \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^e - \frac{3K^\infty (\alpha_d^\infty - \alpha_m^\infty)}{\rho} \text{tr} \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^v - \frac{D_{dT} - D_{mT}}{\rho} \Delta T + \right. \\
& \quad \left. RT \log(\gamma_d Y_d)^{\Gamma_d} - RT \log(\gamma_m Y_m)^{\Gamma_m} \right\} \dot{Y}_d \\
& + \rho \left\{ T \left(\frac{D_{mT}}{\rho} - \frac{D_{pT}}{\rho} - R \log(\gamma_m Y_m)^{\Gamma_m} + R \log(\gamma_p Y_p)^{\Gamma_p} \right) - (\mu_p^0 - \mu_m^0 + (D_{pmd} + D_{md}) \Delta Y_d + \right. \\
& \quad \left. (D_{pmp} + D_{mp}) \Delta Y_p - \frac{3K^0 (\alpha_p^0 - \alpha_m^0)}{\rho} \text{tr} \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^e - \frac{3K^\infty (\alpha_p^\infty - \alpha_m^\infty)}{\rho} \text{tr} \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^v - \frac{D_{pT} - D_{mT}}{\rho} \Delta T + \right. \\
& \quad \left. RT \log(\gamma_p Y_p)^{\Gamma_p} - RT \log(\gamma_m Y_m)^{\Gamma_m} \right\} \dot{Y}_p.
\end{aligned}$$

Equation of diffusion for a species:

$$\rho \dot{Y}_i = v_{ir} M_i R_{dir} [1 - K^{-1} \prod_{i=m,d,p} (\gamma_i Y_i)^{M_i \Gamma_i}] + \mathbf{c}_{rs} \text{tr} \boldsymbol{\sigma}^{an} - \text{div} [-\mathbf{k}_d^H \nabla (\mu_d - \mu_m) - \mathbf{c}_{pm}^{HH} \cdot \nabla (\mu_p - \mu_m) - \mathbf{c}_d^{HT} \nabla T] \quad (10)$$

It is pointed out the fact that \mathbf{J}^q is a function of the quantities ∇T , $\nabla \mu_d$, $\nabla \mu_m$, $\nabla \mu_p$, μ_d , μ_m , μ_p and that the potentials depend on following parameters: Y_d , Y_p , $\text{tr} \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^e$, $\text{tr} \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^v$, T . The coupling linear complementary laws associated with coupling state laws give non linear local equation of diffusion and non linear heat equation. In the expression giving the temperature change Eqn. 9, the quantities for conduction and radiation are established, and also the quantities relating to the traditional mechanical aspect in thermo-viscous-elasticity. The last two quantities correspond to the evolution of the mixture during the chemical reaction. Since the chemical potentials are functions of the mass fractions and of the change of elastic and viscous volume, this dependency appears in the differential equation governing the temperature. Concerning the equation of diffusion Eqn. 10, for the same reason as previously, the modification of the mixture governed mainly by the chemical reaction is also influenced by the state of deformation of the mixture. If a compacting or contracting loading is considered, the diffusion of the species is more or less accelerated. It is also perhaps a second order effect but, if the prediction of the precise evolution of the state of the matter throughout the cure is searched, its taking into account must be considered. The evolution of the species is influenced by the gradient of the temperature, but also by the temperature itself through state laws concerning the chemical potentials.

APPLICATION TO FINITE ELEMENT SIMULATION OF THE CURE OF AN EPOXY RESIN

Modelling approach proposed in this paper is applied to the cure of an LY556 Ciba-Geigy epoxy resin. Experiments data are provided by Jochum [12]. Mass ratios employed are following: 15.789g of LY556 pre-polymer, 14.211g of HY917 hardener. The very low mass of accelerator is neglected for the simulation for further mass ratios evolutions of pre-polymer and hardener. However, effects of accelerator are taken into account by cure kinetics simulations coefficients based on Gotro differential equation of cure kinetics [11]. Thus, aims of the simulation will be the numerical determination of temperature field, displacement field, degree of conversion of the reaction, strain field and stress field during the thermosetting reaction of the LY556 epoxy resin. Precise details for numerical implementations are provided by Rambert [13]. Validity of numerical implementation was first tested with Abaqus 6.3 FEM thermoelastic solutions.

User subroutine element (UEL) description

According to long time of computation induced by viscoelastic calculations exceeding a week, only elastic simulations without species diffusion could be done. UEL developed

contains therefore four degrees of freedom (three axis displacement and temperature). Fortran 77 programming language was used for UEL implementation into the finite element calculation software Abaqus 6.3. The UEL contains quadratic interpolations functions of finite elements, stiffness and viscosity matrix and remainder vector. A 20 nodes isoparametric three-dimensional element with quadratic interpolation functions was necessary to solve the coupling model. Newton method was used in Abaqus to solve differential equations. Integrals were solved with the Gauss method.

Description of the cure to simulate

Fig. 1 shows the experimental device used by Jochum [13] for the cure of the LY556 epoxy resin. Liquid resin is poured into a metallic cylinder up to the half of its capacity. The assembly is airtight and plunged into a sand mould to assume a homogeneous heating of the cylinder by an electric plate. Internal air pressure and temperature are monitored throughout the cure done with a 0.6°C/min ramp followed by an isothermal step around 85°C. A special protocol taking into account gas emission during cure and based on perfect gas rules allows the calculation of volume variations induced by the chemical reaction during the cure cycle. Thus experimental data provided are chemical shrinkage during cure, temperature elevation $T_2(t)$ produced by exothermal effects of thermosetting reaction of epoxy cure and temperature boundary conditions $T_1(t)$ applied by the heating.

Fig. 1: Experimental device for epoxy cure data

Fig. 2: 3D 20 nodes meshing of the resin block

The meshing used is presented on Fig. 2. Only a quarter of the resin block was necessary to be meshed. Outputs were selected on Fig. 2 indicated element. “Element 136” is located close to the center point of cylinder resin block.

RESULTS

FEM cure simulations were done in the field of linear elasticity, without coupling between species diffusion and chemistry according to too long calculation time. Therefore only couplings between chemistry, thermal and mechanics were considered. However, expansion induced by diffusion of species is taken into account. Indirect couplings that consider material parameter evolving with cure kinetics were studied.

Indirect coupling inputs

Initial conditions and material parameters are exposed on table 1.

Table 1: Initial conditions and material parameters

Mechanical	Thermal	Diffusion	Chemical
$E=19.3\text{M Pa}$ $\nu=0.38$ $\rho=1200\text{ kg.m}^{-3}$	$\alpha_T=1.6.10^{-4}\text{ K}^{-1}$ $C_p=\text{several values J K}^{-1}.\text{kg}^{-1}$ $\lambda_T=0.2\text{ W.m}^{-1}.\text{K}^{-1}$	$\alpha_d - \alpha_m=0.04755$ $\alpha_p - \alpha_m=0.04268$	$\frac{U_d M_d}{U_m M_m} = -0.473$ $\frac{U_p M_p}{U_m M_m} = -0.527$
Cure kinetics			
$\frac{dY_m}{dt} = (a_1 e^{-e_1/T} + a_2 e^{-e_1/T} Y_m^m)(1-Y_m)^n$ <p>avec $e_1=6000\text{ K}$, $e_2=7855\text{ K}$, $a_1=1.35.10^3\text{ s}^{-1}$, $a_2=1.77.10^6\text{ s}^{-1}$, $m=0.75$, $n=1.75$</p>			
Initial conditions			
$Y_p^o=0.527$, $Y_d^o=0.473$, $\mu_d^o-\mu_m^o=185.10^3\text{ J.kg}^{-1}$, $\mu_p^o-\mu_m^o=185.10^3\text{ J.kg}^{-1}$, $\sigma_o=0\text{ Pa}$, $s_o=0\text{ J K}^{-1}.\text{kg}^{-1}$, $T_o=291.05\text{ K}$			

Effects of material parameters dependency to cure kinetics were tested by assuming a dependency to degree of conversion of the reaction as shown on Fig. 3. This is certainly questionable for thermal characteristics but seems realistic for mechanical parameters.

Fig. 3: Evolution of specific heat during cure

Temperature and degree of conversion results

Fig. 4 shows temperature history obtained by simulation during the cure. Data are tested with several C_p values in addition to degree of cure dependency.

Fig. 4: Local element 136 temperature and degree of cure history during cure

Temperature evolution is quite similar in the range of Cp considered. Exothermal effect is obtained and is in the right magnitude level (3 - 5%). However, a significant difference of characteristic time is observed. This denotes a strong dependency of simulation results to initial chemical potentials introduced since they are representative of latent heat of the reaction. Consequently, corresponding degree of conversion history is strongly affected in comparison with experimental results.

Cure shrinkage results

Cure simulation results concerning axial strain of the block of resin after deduction of its thermal expansion are representative of chemical shrinkage. Results obtained on element 136 are compared with experimental macroscopic chemical shrinkage established by Jochum using internal pressure and temperature evolutions recorded during cure. Fig. 5 shows very encouraging results obtained by simulation of displacement field. Strain was calculated assuming small perturbation context.

Fig. 5: Chemical shrinkage history during cure

Anyway, these results demonstrate that it is possible with this kind of modelling approach to carry out temperature and strain history inside of a resin block during its cure. Nevertheless disadvantages are in the fact that fine materials parameters are required.

CONCLUSION AND OUTLINES

In this paper, basis of a modelling approach coupling thermal, diffusion, chemical phenomena and the mechanics were established within the framework of the standard generalized mediums in the context of linear viscoelasticity. This approach of generalized standard mediums allows establishing state laws systematically. Nevertheless the taking into account of viscosity and degree of conversion of the chemical reaction are related to the framework of non reversible out of balance thermodynamic processes. A numerical tool coupling mechanical, physical and chemical phenomena is developed on the basis of developments presented above and implemented into an industrial FEM code. Even if a more classical construction has been chosen to simplify the implementation, which is not so completely appropriate for the physical involved phenomena, first results are very positive and made the demonstration of the applicability of this modelling approach to provide local information during the cure. The next step consists to build up the specific free dissipation and potential energy by experimental identifications. This work is under progress at the E.N.S.I.E.T.A institute, namely by DMA-TMA experiments. In addition to this, long-term objective is to build up a predictive tool, able to grasp finely all the process of cure, namely for thick composites.

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